

The Phenotypic Conundrum: The Concept and Details

Harisoorya A. U^{1*} & Vidya N²

^{*1} Research Scholar, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore, Karnataka, INDIA
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0013-2444, E-mail: vishnuau1@gmail.com

² Associate Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore, Karnataka, INDIA
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3390-567X, E-mail: vidyakrithi.n@gmail.com

^{*}Corresponding author's contact number: +918136861791

ABSTRACT

Purpose: *The sickness risk is made up of a variety of common genetic variations with low individual effects as well as rare, highly penetrant genetic variants with larger impacts. We still have a poor grasp of the etiopathogenesis of schizophrenia and genotype-environment interactions, despite recent advances in molecular genetics. Thanks to genome-wide research, we are rapidly improving our understanding of the molecular genetics of schizophrenia. Rare copy number variations (mainly deletions) and frequent SNPs associated with schizophrenia alleles were discovered in this study. However, to order to gain a more exact and comprehensive picture of the genetics of schizophrenia, all-new new study findings must be combined with current discoveries. As a result, the primary goal of this study is to combine the most recent findings with existing knowledge and disseminate that knowledge throughout society to order to better comprehend the molecular underpinnings of schizophrenia.*

Design/Methodology/ Approach: *The paper was constructed using secondary data and information. All data and fresh study findings were gathered from reliable publications and websites. To make the study more intelligible to the general public, a systematic clinical analysis was performed. To get to the conclusions, more than fifteen papers were methodically and extensively analyzed.*

Findings/ Result: *As more genetic codings are discovered, the utilization ratio of a range of systems biology methodologies is likely to lead to the application of molecular constitution a breach in the pathophysiologies of schizophrenia, as well as the creation of new therapies.*

Originality and value: *A unique approach has been adopted to help clinicians and those who work with schizophrenic patients understand the genetic vulnerability to schizophrenia in the most basic and scientific way possible. The materials have been compiled and organized in such a manner that anyone interested in learning more about schizophrenia and its hereditary predispositions can benefit from this article.*

Paper type: *Educational/Interpretive paper*

Keywords: Phenotypic Conundrum, Schizophrenia, Genetics, Bipolar disorder (BPD), Genome-wide association study (GWAS)

1. INTRODUCTION:

Schizophrenia is a life-threatening mental illness, with a lifetime prevalence of 4.0 per 1,000 persons and a morbidity risk of 7.2 per 1,000 [1]. The illness generally begins in adolescence or early adulthood, with occurrence beyond the fifth decade and in childhood being exceedingly rare [2], [3]. Even though males and females have similar rates of schizophrenia, the boys' course is often more severe and starts earlier [4]. The standardized mortality ratio (SMR; the ratio of observed deaths to predicted deaths) for all-cause mortality is greater in people with schizophrenia when compared to the general population [5]. Suicide is the leading cause of mortality in the early stages of the condition, followed by cardiovascular issues later. Schizophrenia generally takes a long time to develop, with different patterns and cognitive impairment. Positive symptoms such as hallucinations and delusions are widespread, as are negative symptoms such as diminished emotions, speech, and interest, as well as

disorganization indications such as changed syntax and behavior. Severe mood symptoms, including as manic and major depressive episodes, are present in many instances.

2. RELATED WORKS:

Many ways have been developed to rule out genetic aspects in the manifestation of schizophrenia and other psychiatric disorders. Because of the rapid advancement of genetic research, it is now possible to identify the genes that contribute to the development of schizophrenia and other psychopathologies. Many monozygotic, dizygotic, and adopted child studies have been conducted in the hopes of determining the etiology of schizophrenia through genotyping and phenotypic analysis.

One of the studies comprised 625 participants who were genotyped for 45 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). In addition to imputation analysis, we conducted single-marker and haplotype-based analyses to broaden the coverage of our genetic markers. Two SNPs were discovered to have strong independent impacts [6]. In this work, the idea of "genes plus environment" is challenged, and an alternative explanation is offered, in which DNA sequence diversity is highlighted together with epigenetic misregulation as a crucial etiopathogenic component [7]. Several important genetic variants that elevate the risk of mental diseases have been uncovered using recent large genomic approaches, such as genome-wide association studies [8]. The temporolimbic-prefrontal brain networks are hypothesized to be disrupted early in schizophrenia. Schizophrenia has been associated with prefrontal dysfunction and an increase in presynaptic striatal DA activity. Table 1 gives some information on this important issue [9].

Table 1: A review of journals/articles on genetics and its relationship to the development of schizophrenia.

S. No.	Focus area/Findings	Year	Reference
1	The potential for genetic vulnerability to schizophrenia in a three-gene cluster area, AS3MT-CNNM2-NT5C2, was investigated in this study. To perform association studies of the targeted areas with schizophrenia, we used a two-stage technique.	2016	Guan F, et al. [10].
2	The involvement of clinically indistinguishable sporadic and familial cases, the discordance of monozygotic twins, the coincidence of peaks of susceptibility with significant endocrine rearrangements, and frequently changing the course of disease severity, among other nonmendelian irregularities of schizophrenia, are all consistent with partial epigenetic stability (metastability) of gene regulation. It's also been claimed that stochastic epigenetic events might account for a significant percentage of phenotypic diversity that has previously been attributed to environmental factors.	2004	Petronis A. [11].
3	Modern genome-wide association studies in Caucasian nations have discovered a link between the NT5C2 variation rs11191580 and schizophrenia (SCZ). Under a dominant genetic model, we verified a link between the rs11191580 polymorphism and SCZ hazard in South Chinese Han.	2007	Li Z, et al. [12].
4	Recent massive genetic techniques, such as genome-wide association studies, have identified several key genetic variations that raise the risk of psychiatric disorders, among which SNPs within or near the vaccinia related kinase 2 (VRK2) gene have gained consistent support for their correlations with multiple psychiatric and neurological disorders, including schizophrenia (SCZ), major depressive disorder (MDD), and genetic generalized anxiety disorder (GAD).	2018	Li M, et al. [13].

5	VRK2 gene expression changes appear to be associated with schizophrenia and PNOS, which is consistent with the results from genome-wide association studies. Decreased VRK2 mRNA levels may be implicated in the underlying processes in schizophrenia spectrum illnesses, according to these findings.	2016	Tesli M, et al. [14].
6	Schizophrenia is thought to be linked to early-onset disruption in the temporolimbic-prefrontal neural networks. Prefrontal dysfunction and elevation of presynaptic striatal DA activity have been linked to schizophrenia, according to brain imaging studies. Recent molecular brain imaging investigations have merged genetic analyses with multimodal neuroimaging to improve our understanding of the disorder's pathophysiological architecture.	2003	Heinz A, Romero B, et al. [15].

Source: Compiled by the author

3. OBJECTIVES:

This paper was written to provide light on schizophrenia and its hereditary susceptibility. It investigates the genetic and non-genetic factors that contribute to the development of schizophrenia and other mental illnesses. The following are the major goals of this article:

1. To get a better understanding of the area of the phenotypic conundrum of schizophrenia.
2. To understand its complex and very underlying genetics.
3. To throw some light on schizophrenia and familial clustering.
4. To identify some information about Darwinien Paradox.

4. METHODOLOGY:

This research is based on secondary clinical data from throughout the world that has been published. Every paper has undergone a systematic clinical analysis to make the subject matter more concise and comprehensible. We used a variety of scientific and approved journals as well as websites to get clinical data.

5. THE PHENOTYPIC CONUNDRUM:

Caseness must be defined before study design considerations may be made. Bipolar disorder (BPD), schizoaffective disorder, and schizophrenia all have some phenotypic similarities, both in terms of symptoms and treatments, with all three disorders responding to some antipsychotic medications. Dementia praecox, as defined by Emil Kraepelin, is a collection of psychotic diseases with a bad prognosis [16]. He classified as manic-depressive psychoses a range of illnesses that encompassed periodic and cyclical insanity, simple mania, and melancholia, all of which he believed did not progress. Dementia praecox and manic-depressive psychoses, according to Kraepelin, have distinct causes. However, reality proved to be more complicated, and in the year 1933, a scientist named Jacob Kasanin developed the term schizoaffective psychosis to describe an illness that combines the symptoms of schizophrenia and affective disorder [17]. Family studies reveal that the clinically midway diagnosis of schizoaffective disorder is more ubiquitous in families derived from probands with schizophrenia as well as in families derived from probands with bipolar disorder as compared to the general population [18], [19]. It is difficult to make out between schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, and schizoaffective disorder [20]. The precise time criteria for affective symptoms in next of kin to schizophrenia symptoms are not established, and it varies according to modern-day classifications [21], [22].

6. GENETICS:

Our basic knowledge of the molecular pathways underlying schizophrenia pathophysiology is still quite inadequate. False starts and dead ends in research have taught the science to be cautious; the biochemical intricacy of schizophrenia is far more than expected. This intricacy also extends to basic Mendelian illnesses, which, while easily evaluated by pedigree analysis, can have a surprising amount of biology. The architecture of schizophrenia, on the other hand, is incomparably more challenging than that of basic hereditary illnesses. In genome-wide linkage

scans, the concept that one or a few common significant gene effects explain schizophrenia was empirically tested, but the results typically fell short of genome-wide significance [18]. It should come as no surprise that schizophrenia is extremely complicated. First, the brain is more convoluted than any other organ; in humans, the number of neuronal interconnections and permutations is very huge, like 2, 10¹⁰ neocortical neurons and 10¹⁴ synapses and our indulgent in the physiological establishment of higher brain activities are quite limited. Second, the lack of well-defined focused, and distinct microscopic neuropathology has made schizophrenia particularly resistant to molecular advancement, but as we will see below, this is changing [23], [24].

Schizophrenia belongs to the complex genetic disorders category of diseases. As new research finds unique disease processes, our understanding of complicated genetic illnesses continues to evolve. A lot of genes are assumed to be implicated in each condition, with each gene having just a little impact on the phenotype. As a result, individual risk variations have little diagnostic prognostic value, and any risk estimates will almost certainly alter in the future as bigger epidemiological samples become available for examination [25]. Interactions between these genes and their products, as well as interactions with environmental risk factors, are thought to be quite likely. However, because of the necessity to account for a large number of statistical comparisons, the investigation of genetic interactions using genome-wide data remains largely unexplored. Our understanding of schizophrenia is changing from oligogenic to polygenic models, but its genetic architecture remains mostly unknown. According to current research, the mutation frequency spectrum contains a mixture of common and unusual mutations. The notion of system disorder, which states that complex illnesses are caused by the breakdown of whole molecular networks rather than faulty gene activity, is gaining traction in the literature [26]. Whether or not this is true for schizophrenia is an empirical question that has yet to be answered.

Changes in DNA sequence have long been thought to be primarily responsible for the transmission of schizophrenia. Twin studies, on the other hand, suggest that an epigenetic mechanism might play a role in the transmission of schizophrenia. The potential of epigenetics, or changes in phenotype not explained by DNA sequence, was initially postulated as an explanation for the inadequate concordance for schizophrenia in monozygotic twins, but due to methodological limitations, it has yet to be confirmed [27],[28].

7. COMPLEX GENETICS:

Our understanding of the molecular pathways underlying schizophrenia pathophysiology is still quite limited. Miscues and dead-ends in research have taught the science to be cautious; the biochemical intricacy of schizophrenia is far more than expected. This intricacy also extends to basic Mendelian illnesses, which, while easily evaluated by pedigree analysis, can have a surprising amount of biology. The architecture of schizophrenia, on the other hand, is incomparably more challenging than that of basic hereditary illnesses. In genome-wide linkage scans, the concept that one or a few common significant gene effects explain schizophrenia was empirically tested, but the results typically fell short of genome-wide significance [29]. It's hardly astonishing that schizophrenia is so complicated. Initially, the brain is more convoluted than any other organ; humans have a staggering amount of neuronal interconnections and permutations (2, 10¹⁰ neocortical neurons and 10¹⁴ synapses), and our understanding of the physiological foundation of higher brain activities is extremely limited. Second, the lack of well-defined focused, and distinct microscopic neuropathology has made schizophrenia particularly resistant to molecular advancement, although as we'll see below, this is changing [30].

Schizophrenia connects to the complex genetic illnesses category of diseases. As new research finds unique disease processes, our understanding of complicated genetic illnesses continues to evolve. Many genes are assumed to be implicated in each condition, with each gene having just a little impact on the phenotype. As a result, individual risk variations have no diagnostic prognostic value, and any risk estimates will almost certainly alter in the future as bigger epidemiological samples become available for investigation. Associations between these genes and their products, as well as interactions with environmental risk factors, are thought to be quite likely. Nevertheless, because of the necessity to account for a large number of statistical comparisons, the investigation of genetic interactions using genome-wide data remains largely unexplored. Our understanding of schizophrenia is changing from oligogenic to polygenic models, but its genetic architecture remains mostly unknown. According to current research, the mutation frequency spectrum contains a mixture of common and unusual mutations. The notion of system disorder, which states that complex illnesses are caused by the breakdown of whole molecular networks rather than faulty gene activity, is gaining traction in the literature. Whether or not this is true for schizophrenia is an empirical issue that has yet to be answered. Changes in DNA sequence have long been thought to be primarily responsible for the transmission of schizophrenia. Twin studies, on the other hand, suggest that an epigenetic mechanism might play a role in the transmission of schizophrenia. Due to methodological problems, the potential of

a role for epigenetics, or changes in phenotype not explained by DNA sequence, was initially presented as an explanation for the inadequate concordance for schizophrenia in monozygotic twins.

8. SCIENTIFIC EVIDENCE FOR ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS TO DEVELOP SCHIZOPHRENIA:

The long-held and widely held idea that the prevalence of schizophrenia is unaffected by geography or time has lately been debunked, paving the way for a surprisingly fruitful period in the research of schizophrenia epidemiology. New epidemiological findings reveal that certain obstetric problems, urban birth or residency, famines, migrant status, and seasonal influences (through prenatal illnesses, such as influenza) all raise the chance of schizophrenia. Other epidemiological research implies that advanced paternal age, as well as cerebral hypoxia and other severe pregnancy and neonatal problems, are contextual significant risk factors [31]. Overall, the panorama of environmental dangers is rich and fast expanding, pointing to a slew of early-stage risk factors. Environmental dangers, even those that are physiologically catastrophic, such as famines, have very few individual consequences. Although the exact pathophysiological links between environmental triggers and schizophrenia are still largely unknown, epidemiological findings can help molecular genetics experiments, such as screening specific genes involved in prenatal nutrition and running serologic assays on epidemiological specimens [32].

9. SCHIZOPHRENIA IS CHARACTERIZED BY FAMILIAL CLUSTERING AN OVERVIEW:

The very first rigorous kinship research for a mental disease was undertaken by Ernst Rudin, who was a follower of Kraepelin but subsequently notoriously became the major scientific head of Nazi eugenics [33]. He knew the data didn't match a simple monogenic Mendelian transmission model, but he overlooked the evidence for further complexity. Since then, several family studies of schizophrenia have been done, with the available data indicating that the child of a parent with schizophrenia has a tenfold increased empirical risk above the general population risk. When a disease risk in a kind of relative is compared to that in the general population, it is commonly referred to as r (if the risk is imparted by an allelic mutation, it is referred to as an allele-specific). The relative risk to siblings of having a proband with the disease is referred to as s . Despite having an identical overall genetic impact, common illnesses have a smaller s than uncommon conditions. A basic Mendelian model predicts that the risk of schizophrenia for a relative of the afflicted proband decays significantly faster than the proportion of genes shared between them. A relative of an afflicted proband's risk for schizophrenia decays significantly faster than the proportion of genes shared between them, which contradicts a basic Mendelian model [34]. Despite this, the majority of instances of schizophrenia in the general community are sporadic, which may appear odd at first [35].

10. ADOPTION STUDIES:

In ways that twin studies cannot, these investigations allow for the separation of genetic and environmental aspects of a condition. The high-risk adoptees' technique assesses adopted kids of schizophrenic parents to see if their chance of developing schizophrenia is increased. These investigations have discovered an increased risk of psychosis in such kids, regardless of whether the parents had schizophrenia before or after adoption, or whether the children were raised by foster parents or in institutions. It was found that offspring of schizophrenia mothers had the same risk whether they were raised by the biological (schizophrenic) parent or an adoptive (non-schizophrenic) parent and that descendants of mothers without schizophrenia did not have an increased risk when raised by psychotic adoptive parents, indicating that the risk travels with the biological rather than the adoptive correlation. Moreover, by examining communication deviance in adoptive parents of high-risk adoptees, adoption research might provide insight into gene-environment connections. The adoptees' family method assesses their adopted and biological families for disease, starting with schizophrenic adoptees and matched control adoptees. These researchers found that biological families of schizophrenic adoptees have higher rates of schizophrenia and schizophrenia spectrum disorders than biological families of control adoptees, despite low and comparable rates in adoptive families of both categories of adoptees [36].

11. TWIN STUDIES:

In twin research, differences between monozygotic (identical) twins are assigned to environmental causes, whereas differences between dizygotic (fraternal) twins are attributed to both genetic and environmental variables. The concordance rate or the likelihood that a second twin will acquire a condition if the proband twin does is a widely used statistic. The fraction of variance explained by genetic variables is known as heritability. Schizophrenia concordance rates for monozygotic twins have been estimated to be approximately 40 to 50 percent, with heritability estimates of around 80 percent. The reader should be aware that heritability is not an estimate of the etiology of the disease per se, but rather of the reason for disease variance in a given population. The hazard of schizophrenia and schizophrenia-related illnesses is identical in the kids of unaffected and afflicted monozygotic twins, implying that the unaffected twins do have a heritable genetic risk for schizophrenia even if they do not manifest the condition (supporting either or both, epigenetics and non-shared environments). DNA methylation

variations have recently been hypothesized as a possible source of monozygotic twin discordance, as well as a mechanism for a range of environmental risk factors for schizophrenia [37].

12. DARWINIEN PARADOX:

Schizophrenia has long been linked to lower fertility, which can be explained by the disorder's behavioral and social traits. Fertility is severely harmed in both men and women, albeit males are more severely affected. Because of Western countries' delayed marriage patterns, decreased fertility is expected to rise, but the age of onset for schizophrenia has remained the same. Natural selection is intended to reduce the population frequency of disease genes that reduce fertility. The frequency of schizophrenia, on the other hand, remains high – considerably greater than that of Mendelian illnesses. Multiple explanations have been presented to explain how schizophrenia circumvents the influence of natural selection (often referred to as the "Darwinian paradox") [38]. Although preliminary observations did not replicate in bigger populations, relatives of schizophrenics may experience compensating rise in infertility. Alternative hypotheses such as heterozygote advantage (any homozygote exhibits poorer fitness compared to the heterozygote, as in sickle cell anemia and antagonist pleiotropy are weakened by the lack of evidence for higher fertility in relatives of schizophrenics [39].

13. GENOME-WIDE ASSOCIATION STUDY (GWAS):

Genome-wide research, when combined with system biology methodologies, produce comprehensive data that is more beneficial in dealing with complicated disorders [40]. GWAS, in contrast to candidate gene studies, examines indicators of common variation across the human genome one at a time, examining all genes and the majority of non-genic areas, whether or not they have been previously implicated by pathogenic theories. Because of the enormous number of tests in a GWAS, the approach is prone to false-positive results; hence, determining an adequate genome-wide significance level is critical. The genome-wide significance threshold, assuming testing for all common SNPs and a value of 5% significance, has been calculated to be about $p < 5 \times 10^{-8}$, [41]. GWAS have been more effective than any other method of discovering novel susceptibility loci for complex illnesses because they cover a larger portion of the human genome. GWAS are based on linkage disequilibrium (LD), which is a non-random statistical correlation of alleles at two or more loci that are typically linked with close physical proximity between genetic markers [42], [43], [44].

14. RARE CNV AND SCHIZOPHRENIA:

CNVs, which are long sequences of genomic deletions and duplications spanning from 1 kb to several Mb, are more likely than SNPs to have phenotypic effects. At 1q21.1, 2p16.3 (NRXN1), 15q11.2, 15q13.2, 16p11.2, and 22q11.21 138–144, evidence for a link between particular uncommon and significant CNVs and schizophrenia is accumulating [45], [46]. Velocardiofacial syndrome (VCFS) is known to be caused by a 3 Mb deletion at 22q11.21 (22qDS), which raises the risk of schizophrenia. All of the CNVs first detected solely in schizophrenia patients (save 22q11.21) were later found in healthy controls, suggesting that the penetrance of these uncommon CNVs may be limited [47]. Exon disruptions, rather than deletions of other portions of NRXN1, are related to schizophrenia, according to the NRXN1 deletions, which exclusively affect this one gene [48].

15. CHALLENGES IN THE AREA OF ASSOCIATION BETWEEN GENES AND SCHIZOPHRENIA:

After more than a quarter-century of effort in schizophrenia molecular genetics, breakthroughs in biotechnology and statistics applied to the analysis of large, well-characterized clinical samples have enabled the finding of individual susceptibility loci with subsequent replication. The scope of this paper does not allow for a detailed explanation of what happens next following a successful GWAS. We've chosen a few topics for debate that have been critical in achieving success thus far and will serve as a basis for future advancement. First, the social context in which research is performed has altered dramatically in recent years. The emphasized posture of a new openness in the study of schizophrenia genetics, in accordance with the initiated NIH policy of extensive GWAS data sharing, is crucial.

For future development, the procedure for following up on GWAS results must be rigorous; replication and precise mapping of related areas are required. Although it is preferable to aggregate GWAS data from different studies, targeted genotyping can still be beneficial, albeit less informative, when some of the samples do not have GWAS data. Because most clinical samples lack the power to detect effect sizes typically found in well-powered GWAS, and because only top-ranking associations are reported, the estimated ORs tend to be inflated; a less biased estimation of ORs necessitates the systematic combination of GWAS and focused replication studies.

16. CONCLUSIONS:

Genetics is a substantial risk factor for schizophrenia, according to pre-molecular and molecular genetics research. Many of the findings from schizophrenia genome-wide association studies have been reproduced, and some of them have gained meta-analytic genome-wide significance. On a variety of levels, the strong connections between schizophrenia and the >100 susceptibility loci, the discovered CNVs, and SNVs, appear promising. Furthermore, the relevance of the hundreds of common alleles with just a minor impact, which does not individually attain significance but collectively comprises a significant polygenic component of schizophrenia risk, should not be overlooked. These findings should, hopefully, pave the path for really unique, practical therapeutic information. However, we should not overlook the following points: (i) associations between common (SNPs) or uncommon (CNVs, SNVs) genetic variants and schizophrenia are statistical facts, not necessarily indexes of causal pathways; and (ii) many of the discovered associations are non-specific to schizophrenia, but rather indicate a genetic vulnerability to a variety of mental disorders. Overall, the intricacies of schizophrenia's etiopathogenesis and genotype-environment interplay are still largely unknown, thus care is still advised when making judgments regarding the amount of the genetic contribution to the disorder's etiology.

REFERENCES:

- [1]. Li, M., Jaffe, A. E., Straub, R. E., Tao, R., Shin, J. H., Wang, Y., ... & Weinberger, D. R. (2016). A human-specific AS3MT isoform and BORCS7 are molecular risk factors in the 10q24. 32 schizophrenia-associated locus. *Nature medicine*, 22(6), 649-656. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [2]. Abashkin, D. A., Kurishev, A. O., Karpov, D. S., & Golimbet, V. E. (2021). Cellular Models in Schizophrenia Research. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 22(16), 851-878. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [3]. Tao, R., Cousijn, H., Jaffe, A. E., Burnet, P. W., Edwards, F., Eastwood, S. L., ... & Kleinman, J. E. (2014). Expression of ZNF804A in human brain and alterations in schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, and major depressive disorder: a novel transcript fetally regulated by the psychosis risk variant rs1344706. *JAMA psychiatry*, 71(10), 1112-1120. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [4]. Bleuler, E., & Jung, C. G. (1908). Komplexe und Krankheitsursachen bei Dementia praecox. *Zentralblatt für Nervenheilkunde und Psychiatrie*, 31(1), 220-227. [Google Scholar](#)
- [5]. Meehl, P. E. (1962). Schizotaxia, schizotypy, schizophrenia. *American psychologist*, 17(12), 827. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [6]. Holzman, P. S. (1989). The use of eye movement dysfunctions in exploring the genetic transmission of schizophrenia. *European archives of psychiatry and neurological sciences*, 239(1), 43-48. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [7]. Nicolini, H. IV. Biología molecular y psiquiatría: Mapeo genético del trastorno obsesivo compulsivo. *Revista de la Facultad de Medicina*, 1(1). 78-91. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [8]. Gottesman, I. I., & Shields, J. (1972). A polygenic theory of schizophrenia. *International Journal of Mental Health*, 1(1-2), 107-115. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [9]. Kendler, K. S., & Zerbin-Rüdin, E. (1996). Abstract and review of "studien über vererbung und entstehung geistiger störungen. I. Zur vererbung und neuentstehung der dementia praecox." (Studies on the inheritance and origin of mental illness: I. To the problem of the inheritance and primary origin of dementia praecox.). *American journal of medical genetics*, 67(4), 338-342. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [10]. Kahn, E. R. M. E. (Ed.). (2013). *Studien über Vererbung und Entstehung Geistiger Störungen: IV. Schizoid und Schizophrenie im Erbgang* 36(1), 392-409. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [11]. Schulz, B. (1933). Zur erbpathologie der schizophrenie. *Zeitschrift für die gesamte Neurologie und Psychiatrie*, 143(1), 175-293. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)

- [12]. Kallmann, F. J. (1938). The genetics of schizophrenia. *J. A. psychology* 28(2), 113-129. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [13]. Henriksen, M. G., Nordgaard, J., & Jansson, L. B. (2017). Genetics of schizophrenia: overview of methods, findings and limitations. *Frontiers in human neuroscience*, 11(1), 322-432. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [14]. Kallmann, F. J. (1946). The genetic theory of schizophrenia: An analysis of 691 schizophrenic twin index families. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 103(3), 309-322. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [15]. Slater, E. (1953). Psychotic and neurotic illnesses in twins.(Med. Res. Council Special Rep. Ser., No. 278.)(Available from British Information Services, 30 Rockefeller Plaza, New York.). *SLATER E. Spec Rep Ser Med Res Counc (G B)*. 278(2),1-38. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [16]. Rosenthal, D. (1959). Some factors associated with concordance and discordance with respect to schizophrenia in monozygotic twins. *Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease*. 28(3), 89-95. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [17]. Fromer, M., Pocklington, A. J., Kavanagh, D. H., Williams, H. J., Dwyer, S., Gormley, P., ... & O'Donovan, M. C. (2014). De novo mutations in schizophrenia implicate synaptic networks. *Nature*, 506(7487), 179-184. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [18]. Glessner, J. T., Reilly, M. P., Kim, C. E., Takahashi, N., Albano, A., Hou, C., ... & Hakonarson, H. (2010). Strong synaptic transmission impact by copy number variations in schizophrenia. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 107(23), 10584-10589. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [19]. Purcell, S. M., Moran, J. L., Fromer, M., Ruderfer, D., Solovieff, N., Roussos, P., ... & Sklar, P. (2014). A polygenic burden of rare disruptive mutations in schizophrenia. *Nature*, 506(7487), 185-190. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [20]. Richards, A. L., Leonenko, G., Walters, J. T., Kavanagh, D. H., Rees, E. G., Evans, A., ... & O'Donovan, M. C. (2016). Exome arrays capture polygenic rare variant contributions to schizophrenia. *Human molecular genetics*, 25(5), 1001-1007. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [21]. Kraepelin, E. (1921). Manic depressive insanity and paranoia. *The Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease*, 53(4), 350-373. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [22]. Kasanin, J. A. C. O. B. (1933). The acute schizoaffective psychoses. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 90(1), 97-126. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [23]. Maier, W., Lichtermann, D., Minges, J., Hallmayer, J., Heun, R., Benkert, O., & Douglas, F. L. (1993). Continuity and discontinuity of affective disorders and schizophrenia: results of a controlled family study. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 50(11), 871-883. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [24]. Maier, W., Lichtermann, D., Franke, P., Heun, R., Falkai, P., & Rietschel, M. (2002). The dichotomy of schizophrenia and affective disorders in extended pedigrees. *Schizophrenia research*, 57(2-3), 259-266. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [25]. Gershon, E. S., DeLisi, L. E., Hamovit, J., Nurnberger, J. I., Maxwell, M. E., Schreiber, J., ... & Guroff, J. J. (1988). A controlled family study of chronic psychoses: schizophrenia and schizoaffective disorder. *Archives of general psychiatry*, 45(4), 328-336. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [26]. Gershon, E. S., Hamovit, J., Guroff, J. J., Dibble, E., Leckman, J. F., Sceery, W., ... & Bunney, W. E. (1982). A family study of schizoaffective, bipolar I, bipolar II, unipolar, and normal control probands. *Archives of General psychiatry*, 39(10), 1157-1167. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)

- [27]. Kendler, K. S., McGuire, M., Gruenberg, A. M., O'hare, A., Spellman, M., & Walsh, D. (1993). The Roscommon family study: I. Methods, diagnosis of probands, and risk of schizophrenia in relatives. *Archives of general psychiatry*, 50(7), 527-540. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [28]. Vallès, V., Van Os, J., Guillamat, R., Gutiérrez, B., Campillo, M., Gento, P., & Fañanás, L. (2000). Increased morbid risk for schizophrenia in families of in-patients with bipolar illness. *Schizophrenia research*, 42(2), 83-90. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [29]. Heckers, S. (2009). Is schizoaffective disorder a useful diagnosis?. *Current psychiatry reports*, 11(4), 332-337. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [29]. Spitzer, R. L., Endicott, J., & Robins, E. (1978). Research diagnostic criteria: rationale and reliability. *Archives of general psychiatry*, 35(6), 773-782. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [30]. Nurnberger, J. I., Blehar, M. C., Kaufmann, C. A., York-Cooler, C., Simpson, S. G., Harkavy-Friedman, J., ... & Reich, T. (1994). Diagnostic interview for genetic studies: rationale, unique features, and training. *Archives of general psychiatry*, 51(11), 849-859. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [31]. Ng, M. Y., Levinson, D. F., Faraone, S. V., Suárez, B. K., DeLisi, L. E., Arinami, T., ... & Lewis, C. M. (2009). Meta-analysis of 32 genome-wide linkage studies of schizophrenia. *Molecular psychiatry*, 14(8), 774-785. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [32]. Sporns, O., Tononi, G., & Kötter, R. (2005). The human connectome: a structural description of the human brain. *PLoS computational biology*, 1(4), 42-62. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [33]. Drachman, D. A. (2005). Do we have brain to spare?. *Neurology*, 64(12), 20-40. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [34]. Kraft, P., & Hunter, D. J. (2009). Genetic risk prediction—are we there yet?. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 360(17), 1701-1703. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [35]. Schadt, E. E. (2009). Molecular networks as sensors and drivers of common human diseases. *Nature*, 461(7261), 218-223. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [36]. Petronis, A. (2004). The origin of schizophrenia: genetic thesis, epigenetic antithesis, and resolving synthesis. *Biological psychiatry*, 55(10), 965-970. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [37]. Roth, T. L., Lubin, F. D., Sodhi, M., & Kleinman, J. E. (2009). Epigenetic mechanisms in schizophrenia. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-General Subjects*, 1790(9), 869-877. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [38]. Ng, M. Y., Levinson, D. F., Faraone, S. V., Suárez, B. K., DeLisi, L. E., Arinami, T., ... & Lewis, C. M. (2009). Meta-analysis of 32 genome-wide linkage studies of schizophrenia. *Molecular psychiatry*, 14(8), 774-785. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [39]. Clarke, M. C., Harley, M., & Cannon, M. (2006). The Role of Obstetric Events in Schizophrenia. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, 32(1), 3-8. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [40]. Cannon, M., Jones, P. B., & Murray, R. M. (2002). Obstetric complications and schizophrenia: historical and meta-analytic review. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 159(7), 1080-1092. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [41]. Brown, A. S., & Susser, E. S. (2008). Prenatal nutritional deficiency and risk of adult schizophrenia. *Schizophrenia bulletin*, 34(6), 1054-1063. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [42]. Gejman, P. V. (1997). Ernst Rüdin and Nazi euthanasia: another stain on his career. *American journal of medical genetics*, 74(4), 455-6. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)

- [43]. Kendler, K. S., & Zerbin-Rüdin, E. (1996). Abstract and review of "studies on heredity and the development of mental disorders. I. For the inheritance and development of dementia praecox." (Studies on the inheritance and origin of mental illness: I. To the problem of the inheritance and primary origin of dementia praecox.). *American journal of medical genetics*, 67(4), 338-342. [Google Scholar↗](#) [Crossref↗](#)
- [44]. McGue, M., Gottesman, I. I., & Rao, D. C. (1983). The transmission of schizophrenia under a multifactorial threshold model. *American Journal of Human Genetics*, 35(6), 1161-1184. [Google Scholar↗](#) [Crossref↗](#)
- [45]. Yang, J., Visscher, P. M., & Wray, N. R. (2010). Sporadic cases are the norm for complex disease. *European Journal of Human Genetics*, 18(9), 1039-1043. [Google Scholar↗](#) [Crossref↗](#)
- [46]. Wender, P. H., Rosenthal, D., Kety, S. S., Schulsinger, F., & Welner, J. (1974). Crossfostering: A research strategy for clarifying the role of genetic and experiential factors in the etiology of schizophrenia. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 30(1), 121-128. [Google Scholar↗](#) [Crossref↗](#)
- [47]. Coyle, J. T., Balu, D., Puhl, M., & Konopaske, G. (2016). A Perspective on the history of the concept of "disconnectivity" in schizophrenia. *Harv Rev Psychiatry*, 24(2), 80-86. [Google Scholar↗](#) [Crossref↗](#)
- [48]. Kendler, K. S., Gruenberg, A. M., & Kinney, D. K. (1994). Independent diagnoses of adoptees and relatives as defined by DSM-III in the provincial and national samples of the Danish Adoption Study of Schizophrenia. *Archives of general psychiatry*, 51(6), 456-468. [Google Scholar↗](#) [Crossref↗](#)